

Metal Complexes of some Model Peptide Derivatives. Part-XI. Mixed Ligand Complex Formation of Copper(II) with Salicyloylglycine and Typical Ligands

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Ternary complexes consisting of a metal ion and two different ligands other than the solvent have provided very useful and simple models for understanding the roles of metal ions in biological systems, which are rather complex in nature¹⁻⁵. Considering the various biological activities⁶ of salicyloyl amide derivatives, salicyloylglycine, (*o*) HOC₆H₄CONHCH₂COOH (hereafter, SGH₂) has been chosen as a ligand for studying such higher order metal-ligand equilibria with a view to elucidate the modes of its metal binding in the presence of typical ligands. The present communication describes the results of an equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} ion with salicyloylglycine and typical ligands, viz. pyridine (py), benzimidazole (bz), acetate (a⁻) and bipyridine (bipy).

Results and Discussion

For the evaluation stability constants of mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes by the SCOGS programme⁷, the complex formation may be assumed to take place according to

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[\text{Cu}_p \text{ A}_q \text{ B}_r (\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{Cu}]^p [\text{A}]^q [\text{B}]^r [\text{OH}]^s} \quad (1)$$

where, A stands for SGH₂ ligand species, B for the other ligand species, py, bz, a⁻ or bipy as the case may be. *p*, *q*, *r* and *s* are stoichiometric numbers; *p*, *q* and *r* are usually positive numbers or zero, *s* is a negative number for a protonic species and a positive number for a hydroxo species. Preliminary estimates of all the binary constants, obtained by least-square method⁸, were further refined by the SCOGS⁷ programme. Complex species described in

Table 1 were assumed to prevail in the complexation equilibria. Ionic product of water (p*K*_w) as in 1 : 1 ethanol-water medium at 30 ± 1° was obtained from literature⁹.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIES OF Cu_pA_qB_r(OH)_s COMPLEXES IN THE TERNARY Cu^{II}–SGH₂–A SYSTEMS (WHERE A = a⁻ py, bz and bipy; B = SGH₂–LIGAND SPECIES)

Stoichiometry Cu _p A _q B _r (OH) _s *	Cu (<i>p</i>)	A (<i>q</i>)	B (<i>r</i>)	OH (<i>s</i>)
AH ₂	0	1	0	-2
AH	0	1	0	-1
SGH ₂	0	0	1	-2
SGH	0	0	1	-1
Cu(OH)	1	0	0	1
Cu(OH) ₂	1	0	0	2
Cu(A)	1	1	0	0
Cu(H ₋₁ SGH)	1	0	1	0
Cu(H ₋₁ SG)	1	0	1	1
Cu(H ₋₁ SG)(OH)	1	0	1	2
Cu(H ₋₁ SGH)(A)	1	1	1	0
Cu(H ₋₁ SG)(A)	1	1	1	1

*AH₂ = bipyH₂⁺; AH = bipyH⁺, pyH⁺, acH⁺; A = bipy, py, bz, a⁻; SGH₂ = neutral ligand (COOH, OH, CONH); SGH = uninegative anion (COO⁻, OH, CONH); H₋₁SGH = dinegative anion (COO⁻, OH, CO⁻), H₋₁SG = trinegative anion (COO⁻, O⁻, CO⁻).

Two types of 1 : 1 Cu : SGH₂ complexes, viz. Cu(H₋₁SGH)(H₂O)₂ and Cu(H₋₁SG)(H₂O) were identified^{10,11} in the binary systems with 1 : 5 and 1 : 1 Cu : SGH₂ ratio respectively. The H₋₁SGH²⁻ ligand ion provided bidentate (O⁻, N⁻) chelation using the carboxylate oxygen atom and the deprotonated

amide nitrogen atom, having the phenolic OH group uncoordinated and hydrogen bonded (1). The $H_{-1}SG^{3-}$ ligand ion, on the other hand, provides terdentate ($\bar{O}, \bar{N}, \bar{O}$) chelation using the carboxylate oxygen atom, deprotonated amide nitrogen atom and the phenolate oxygen atom (2).

Stabilities of these two types of binary complexes were different (Table 2) due to their different structures. Terdentate chelated complex, $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(H_2O)$ was characterised by its higher stability constant.

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND and Cu^{II} -LIGAND BINARY and TERNARY CONSTANTS*

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$; medium : 50% (v/v) ethanol-water, $I = 0.2 M$ ($NaNO_3$)

(a) Proton-ligand constants

	bipy H_2^{2+}	py H^+	bz H^+	acH	SGH ₂
pK_2^H	2.28	—	—	—	3.98
pK_1^H	3.37	5.34	5.66	4.42	8.83

(b) Hydrolytic constants of Cu^{2+} (aq.) ion

	$\log K_{Cu}^H$	$\log K_{Cu}^{2H}$
	-5.94	-12.00

(c) Cu^{2+} -SGH₂ binary constants

$\log K_{Cu+SGH}^{2H}$	$\log K_{Cu(H_{-1}SG)}^{Cu}$	$\log K_{Cu(H_{-1}SG)(OH)}^{Cu}$
-2.08	15.50	6.93

(d) Cu^{2+} -A binary and Cu^{2+} -A-SGH₂ ternary constants

A	bipy	py	bz	ac ⁻
$\log K_{Cu(A)}^{Cu}$	8.00	2.86	3.26	1.76
$\log \beta_{Cu(H_{-1}SGH)(A)}$	11.18	—	—	—
$\log \beta_{Cu(H_{-1}SG)(A)}$	—	18.76	19.16	16.66
$\Delta \log K_{Cu}$	+1.10	+0.40	+0.40	-0.60
$\log K_d$	10.62	3.04	2.64	5.14

* Limits of error in the constants : ± 0.02 to ± 0.06 in log units.

A large number of complex species were identified in the ternary Cu^{II} -SGH₂-A systems (A = py, bz, ac⁻). As all these three ligands were monodentate, the $H_{-1}SG^{3-}$ ligand ion had the scope for providing terdentate ($\bar{O}, \bar{N}, \bar{O}$) chelation to Cu^{II} ion in the ternary $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(A)$ complexes (2). $Cu(A)$ complexes for these systems were formed in small amounts at the early stages of complex formation (pH 3–6). The binary $Cu(H_{-1}SGH)$ complex was not identifiable. The $Cu(H_{-1}SG)$ complex made its first appearance around pH 5, and passed through a wide maxima in the pH range (6–9). It was quite interesting to note that the ternary $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(A)^-$ complexes were major (≈ 50 –60%) copper-containing species in the region of biological pH (7.0–7.5) in the two systems, $Cu^{II}/SGH_2/py$ and $Cu^{II}/SGH_2/bz$ (where, the A ligands coordinated Cu^{II} with heterocyclic tertiary N-atoms as were the prototypes of the imidazole nitrogen atoms of the histidine residue in the proteins. On the other hand, under the same condition the ternary $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(ac^-)^{2-}$ complex was formed only in negligibly small amounts in the $Cu^{II}/SGH_2/ac^-$ system, where the ac⁻ ligand coordinated Cu^{II} with its carboxylate oxygen atom. The favoured formation of ternary $Cu^{II}/SG/(py$ or bz) complexes over $Cu^{II}/SG/ac^-$, was of course, due to the delocalisation of π -electron cloud of the Cu-N (\bar{N} amide) bonds over to the aromatic π -systems of py and bz ligands. Ternary hydroxo complexes, $Cu(A)(OH)$ were formed in small amounts (10–20%) at lower pH values (pH \approx 4). At higher pH values, the hydroxo complexes dominated in all the three systems to such an extent that the major (≈ 80 %) copper-containing species at pH 10 was the ternary hydroxo complex, $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(OH)^{2-}$ ion. The simple hydroxide, $Cu(OH)_2$ was also present in very small amounts (< 20%). Concentration profiles (Fig. 1) of Cu^{II} , the ligand ion, SGH⁻ and those of $Cu(A)$, $Cu(H_{-1}SG)$ and $Cu(A)(H_{-1}SG)$ indicated the formation of the binary complexes according to equilibria (2) and (3),

and the formation of ternary $Cu(H_{-1}SG)(A)$ complexes according to equilibria (4) and (5),

Charges were omitted for simplicity.

At pH > 8, the concentration of ternary hydroxo complex, Cu(H₋₁SG)(OH), increased sharply, obviously due to deprotonation of coordinated water in the complex, Cu(H₋₁SG)(H₂O). At still higher pH (> 9.5), the ternary Cu(H₋₁SG)(A) complexes also contributed to the hydroxo complex formation according to

Rise in the concentration of free A ligands at higher pH (Fig. 1) also supported the equilibria (6). Presence of small amount of Cu(OH)⁺ and Cu(OH)₂

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II}-py-SGH₂ system : (1) SGH₂, (2) SGH⁻, (3) SG²⁻, (4) pyH⁺, (5) Cu(OH)⁺, (6) Cu(OH)₂, (F_M) Cu²⁺, (7) Cu(H₋₁SG)⁻, (8) Cu(H₋₁SG)(OH)²⁻, (9) Cu(py)²⁺, (10) Cu(H₋₁SG)(py)⁻, (11) Cu(py)(OH)⁺ and (12) py.

throughout the pH range provided further evidence of the antidisproportionation equilibria (5). The antidisproportionation equilibrium constant ($\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$) was calculated using the relation³,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}} = \log \beta_{\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{SG)(A)}}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{Cu(A)}}^{\text{Cu}} - \log K_{\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{SG)}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (7)$$

The constant, $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ characterised the coordination tendency of the A ligands toward Cu(H₋₁SG) relative to Cu²⁺(aq.) ion or the coordination tendency of H₋₁SG³⁻ ligand ions to Cu(A) relative to Cu²⁺(aq.) ions. The dissociation constants ($\log K_d$) of the ternary complexes, Cu(H₋₁SG)(A) could be calculated using the relations,

$$\log K_d = \log K_{\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{SG)(OH)}}^{\text{Cu}} - \log \beta_{\text{Cu(H}_{-1}\text{SG)(A)}}^{\text{Cu}} + pK_w \quad (8)$$

Examination of species distribution curves (Fig. 2) of ternary Cu²⁺/(bipy)/SGH₂ system showed that almost 100% of copper was present in the form of the binary Cu(bipy)²⁺ complex at pH < 5.5. Binary Cu(H₋₁SGH) or Cu(H₋₁SG)⁻ complexes were practically non-existent in the entire pH range studied.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II}-bipy-SGH₂ system : (1) SGH₂, (2) SGH⁻, (3) SG²⁻, (4) bipyH⁺, (5) Cu(OH)⁺, (6) Cu(OH)₂, (F_M) Cu²⁺, (7) Cu(H₋₁SG)⁻, (8) Cu(H₋₁SG)(OH)²⁻, (9) Cu(bipy)²⁺, (10) Cu(bipy)(H₋₁SGH) and (11) bipy.

Distribution profiles of the ligand, SGH⁻ ion and those of the complexes Cu(bipy)²⁺ and Cu(bipy)(H₋₁SG)⁻ suggested the formation of the ternary Cu(bipy)(H₋₁SG)⁻ complex according to

As the strongly coordinating bipy ligand blocked two of the four coordination positions around the square planar Cu^{II} ion, the H₋₁SGH²⁻ ion in the ternary Cu(bipy)(H₋₁SGH) complex provided

bidentate (\bar{O} , \bar{N}) chelation (3) as in the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SGH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ complexes (1).

Concentration of the ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SG})^-$, increased sharply at $\text{pH} > 5.5$ and passed through a wide maxima ($\approx 95\%$) around $\text{pH} 7.5\text{--}9.0$ and then gradually decreased with concomitant appearance of the ternary hydroxocomplex, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SG})(\text{OH})^{2-}$ and free bipy ligand species at pH values > 9.5 . This suggested the dissociation of the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SG})^-$ complex at higher pH according to equilibria of the type (6), where, $\text{A} = \text{bipy}$. $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ and $\log K_{\text{d}}$ could be calculated accordingly using the relations (7) and (8) respectively.

Positive value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ for $\text{A} = \text{bipy}$, py and bz provided evidence of favoured formation of ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SG})(\text{A})$ complexes over the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{A})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{SG})$ complexes, obviously due to $\text{Cu}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{A}(\pi)$ electron delocalisation. $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ value for $\text{A} = \text{a}\bar{c}$ was negative, as such π -electron delocalisation was not possible with the $\text{a}\bar{c}$ ligand.

Experimental

The ligand, SGH_2 , was prepared and purified according to the procedure described earlier¹⁰. The procedure for the pH -metric measurement was the same as described earlier¹⁰. Solutions of following compositions were prepared for the equilibrium study : (a), $0.01 (M) \text{HNO}_3$; (b), (a) + $0.001\text{--}0.002 (M) \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; (c), (a) + $0.01 (M) \text{SGH}_2$; (d), (c) + $0.001\text{--}0.002 (M) \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; (e), (a) + $0.002 (M) \text{SGH}_2$; (f), (e) + $0.002 (M) \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; (g), (a) + $0.002 (M) \text{A}$ ligands in the form of AH^+ or AH_2^{2+} ;

(h), (g) + $0.002 (M) \text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; (i), (h) + $0.002 (M) \text{SGH}_2$. Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium. Requisite amounts of NaNO_3 were placed in each solution to maintain a constant ionic strength ($I = 0.2 M$). All the solutions were titrated with a carbonate-free $0.131 M \text{NaOH}$ in the same solvent medium and having the desired ionic strength at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated). The pH , volume (of NaOH) data were subjected to the SCOGS programme⁷, run by a PC-XT computer system

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